

AQUIFER CHARACTERIZATION BY ACTIVE HEAT TRACER USING DIRECT PUSH FIBER OPTICS

Cynthia Lee¹, Nataline Simon², Jérôme de la Bernardie², Jean-Marc Ballard¹, Olivier Bour², René Lefebvre¹

¹. Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Centre Eau Terre Environnement, 490 rue de la Couronne, Québec, Canada

². Univ Rennes, CNRS, Géosciences Rennes, UMR 6118, 35000 Rennes, France

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Abstract

The potential and limitations of heat tracing using fiber optics active Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) were tested at three sites in the Valcartier deltaic aquifer under natural flow conditions. The sites were selected on the basis of different expected ranges of horizontal groundwater fluxes. Fiber optics cables collocated with Cone Penetration Tests (CPT) were installed by direct push adjacent to soil cores and observation wells. Heat tracing quantified groundwater fluxes and thermal properties, which were compared to lab and field measurements. Preliminary results indicate that the temperature profiles are correlated with the stratigraphy defined by the CPT soundings.

1. Introduction

Despite their potential, temperature and heat tracing have seldom been used to characterize aquifers and develop hydrogeological numerical models (Anderson 2005). Recent advances in fiber optics and Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) systems have opened new possibilities for the use of temperature in hydrogeology, which has led to renewed interest in heat tracing (Selker et al. 2006; Bakker et al. 2015; Bense et al. 2016; des Tombe 2019). However, the approaches to be used to get the full benefit from DTS still require further developments. The Valcartier deltaic aquifer is well suited for studying the potential of fiber optic DTS because it has been extensively studied due to a major trichloroethylene contamination problem (Ouillon et al. 2008 & 2010).

2. Methods and techniques

The Valcartier heat tracing experiment involved a wide range of complementary field and lab work aiming to assess both the potential and limitations of heat tracing using active DTS under natural flow conditions: direct push installation of fiber optics at three sites with different expected ranges of groundwater flux, cone penetration tests (CPT) collocated with fiber optics to provide high-resolution stratigraphic profiles, soil coring to measure thermal and hydraulic properties in the lab, direct push long-screened well to measure hydraulic

properties, and downgradient observation wells to compare the velocity of groundwater to the indications provided by DTS.

At Site B, the repeatability of fiber optics DTS for the estimation of groundwater fluxes was tested. Two fiber optic cables, FO-B1 and FO-B2, were installed 10-meters apart by direct push. Active DTS was performed by heating the steel sheath around each fiber optic cable. The cable was heated for 73 hours, after which steady state was assumed to have been reached. The resulting thermal responses can be used to characterize both hydraulic flow and thermal properties along vertical profiles.

3. Results & Discussion

Preliminary results show that active heating can generate changes that are detectable with fiber optic DTS within the temperature profile. **Fig. 1** below shows the temperature response at four different depths along the fiber optic cable installed at site FO-B2. The hydraulic properties at each of these depths are different, as the material belongs to a different hydrofacies based on their CPT response.

Figure 1. Temperature response curves at depths with different aquifer materials as characterized by their CPT response corresponding to a distinct hydrofacies (HF); HF4 and HF2 have respectively the coarsest and finest grain sizes. Hydrofacies classification used the method developed by Fauveau (2006) (see also Ouillon et al. 2008).

Figure 1 shows that the temperature response varies according to the different hydrofacies vertically present along the fiber optics DTS cable. More data interpretation is needed to explain this correlation, but it can be inferred that groundwater flux is controlled by hydraulic properties and that the temperature response is strongly sensitive to that flux. Detailed quantitative interpretation is needed to support this conclusion.

Planned future work includes laboratory work on soil samples to constrain hydraulic and thermal properties, proper verification and calibration of temperature data from the fiber optics, hydraulic testing in an observation well as well as numerical modelling of Site B where the repeatability tests were done.

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References

- Anderson MP (2005) Heat as a ground water tracer. *Groundwater* 43(6): 951-968.
- Bakker M, Caljé R, Schaars F, van der Made KJ & de Haas S (2015) An active heat tracer experiment to determine groundwater velocities using fiber optic cables installed with direct push equipment. *Water Resources Research* 51(4): 2760-2772.
- Bense V, Read T, Bour O, Le Borgne T, Coleman T, Krause S, Chalari A, Mondanos M, Ciocca F & Selker J (2016) Distributed Temperature Sensing as a downhole tool in hydrogeology. *Water Resources Research* 52(12): 9259-9273.

des Tombe BF, Bakker M, Smits F, Schaars F & van der Made K-J (2019) Estimation of the variation in specific discharge over large depth using Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) measurements of the heat pulse response. *Water Resources Research* 55(1):811-826.

Fauveau, E (2006). *Caractérisation hydrogéologique et identification de faciès des dépôts meubles par enfoncement direct et forage par rotoperçusion*. M.Sc. thesis, Université du Québec, Institut national de la recherche scientifique, Québec, 170 p.

Ouellon T, Lefebvre R, Marcotte D, Boutin A, Blais V & Parent M (2008) Hydraulic conductivity heterogeneity of a local deltaic aquifer system from the kriged 3D distribution of hydrofacies from borehole logs, Valcartier, Canada. *Journal of Hydrology* 351: 71-86.

Ouellon T, Lefebvre R, Blais V, Racine C & Ballard JM (2010). Synthèse du contexte hydrogéologique et de la problématique du TCE dans le secteur Valcartier, Québec, Canada. Research report R-961, INRS, Centre - Eau Terre Environnement, ISBN 978-2-89146-560-1, 119 p.

Selker JS, Thevenaz L, Huwald H, Mallet A, Luxemburg W, de Giesen NV, Stejskal M, Zeman J, Westhoff M & Parlange MB (2006) Distributed fiber-optic temperature sensing for hydrologic systems. *Water Resources Research* 42(12): 8.